

Shock Waves from a Lightning Discharge

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1. ABSTRACT

The analytical and numerical analysis of lightning direct effects on composite structures has mainly been focused on thermo-electric effects of different lightning current components. Mechanical forces created by the electric current flow, by blasting of materials (epoxy resin, metallic protection, coatings) or by shock waves caused by a supersonic expansion of the plasma channel have rarely been taken into account so far. The objective of this paper is a description of lightning shock waves caused by a rapid temperature rise of the lightning plasma channel due to resistive Joule heating. In this context it is first of all necessary to understand the underlying physical mechanisms of this effect. Furthermore, theoretical models for the interpretation of experimental tests as well as for reliable prediction of the magnitude of the shock wave pressure pulses have to be provided. Finally, the temporal and spatial propagation of the shockwaves and pressures that are needed as input for the simulation of mechanical damage prediction of composite structures are derived from semi-analytical models and computational fluid dynamics (CFD). It is shown that the strong shockwave approximation, which provides reliable results for the very early stage of shock wave formation, is perfectly adequate to correctly describe the mechanical damage of composite structures.

2. INTRODUCTION

Reliable numerical methods for damage assessment of lightning discharges attached to composite structures are obviously of major interest regarding aircraft safety. The underlying physics is now relatively well known (e.g., [1]), even if it is very complex in detail. Desirable would be a comprehensive numerical model that features at the one hand a magneto-hydrodynamic (MHD) compressible code for the description of the arc dynamics together with the associated phenomena of radiation, shockwaves, magnetic forces and interface physics including surface explosion effects due to a vaporizing lightning protection layer confined by the inertia of a possible paint or cover layer. On the other hand, the code should also include a coupling to a state of the art bulk dynamics code with sophisticated failure models, typically a commercial finite element code. Literature keeps reporting advances in incorporating ever more physics [2]. However, a complete simulation system, especially when considering compressible MHD-plasma problems along with high peak current loads of return strokes, is still a demanding task [3]. Numerical stability is a major concern and codes are not readily available. From the engineer's point of view, a practical approach is to disentangle the physics into simpler models that calculate individual contributions to mechanical and thermal loads and to apply them additively to a transient finite element

model of the composite structure [4]. We refer to the work in [5] as a comprehensive overview of the current state of methodologies.

Surface damage of protected composite structures is commonly attributed to thermal effects, i.e., heating, melting, vaporization of the metallic lightning protection layer and degradation of adjacent layers. A thermoelectric framework has proven to give realistic estimations of the evolution of the degraded area or, respectively, the degradation radius [6].

Bulk mechanical failure arises mainly due to the following mechanical surface loads: First, when a metallic protection layer undergoes vaporization, the pressure is largely enhanced via the inertia of a cover layer or paint. The magnitude of this surface explosion load depends mainly on the specific weight of surface layer. This surface explosion can be accounted for in a one-dimensional semi-analytical model proposed in Refs. [6] and [9]. Second, the magnetic pressure (strictly speaking the Lorentz forces contributions) is considered as a small but not negligible load contribution. It originates from the high current amplitudes in the pulse components impressed on the conducting lightning protection layer. The magnitude and spatial variation can readily be estimated from the current wave form, but the degradation radius must be known as function of time [4]. Finally, we have the contributions from the shock waves caused by the supersonic expansion of the hot plasma channel [11]-[14]. The primary purpose of this paper is to provide an efficient, yet sufficient approach for the estimation of the magnitude and the temporal evolution of shock waves generated by transient components of lightning strike discharges.

Regarding the shock wave pressure, it is generally accepted that the return stroke current heats the weakly ionized channel by Joule resistive heating. This weakly ionized channel created by the preceding stepped or dart leader is heated from temperatures well below 10 000 K up to near 30 000 K [15]. This rapid temperature rise in a few μs causes a rapid increase of the plasma pressure, since the plasma density cannot decrease substantially within this short time period. From laboratory measurements of long air-sparks, the average channel pressure of a return stroke was estimated by Orville [16] to be about 10 atm during the first few μs . However, the overpressure decreases rapidly so the equilibrium pressure is reached within 10 μs to 40 μs . The remnant of the plasma channel cools slowly down by different loss mechanisms and becomes electrically low-conducting at temperatures below 4000 K [17] roughly 100 ms later. The generated overpressure gives rise to the rapid expansion of the plasma channel and therefore to the formation of a shock wave that propagates outward at supersonic speed.

The experimental database about shock waves caused by electric discharges is not very broad. This is particularly true for lightning thunder as discussed by Few [18]. Few summarized several measured laboratory shock front

overpressures and compared them with different theoretical findings. As a result it can be stated that

- The variance of the measured values is rather large.
- The fitting to the theories is anything else but good.
- The measured laboratory values of the peak pressure are rather low ($\Delta p \leq 0.1$ atm) and correspond to the transition from the shock wave to the acoustic wave.

The measured laboratory data describes the propagation of the shock front in the weak region and does not cover the strong shock wave propagation range near the arc discharge.

Data from laboratory experiments on atmospheric high energy sparks with measurements of pressure close to the burning arc [20] show at least, that the shockwave separates at the very early stage of plasma channel formation. Pressure amplitudes were consistent with semi-analytical models in the weak-shock-wave regime [19] and a linear relationship was found between electric spark energy, and shock wave energy, the latter being only a very small portion of the total deposited energy (of the order of 1% to 2%). Hence, models that approximate the lightning as a line source should be applicable for practical concerns, at least for the weak shockwave regime, which can be also concluded from early fundamental work, see e.g., [11]. Implications of the line source approximation in the very early stage of arc formation are discussed in [21] for an ideal gas. Their results indicate that beyond shock wave radii on the order of a few millimeters for typical return waveforms, no major errors are to be expected.

The present work focuses on the question whether the relatively simple solution of a strong shock wave with a line source initial condition is sufficient to describe the shock wave loads on composite structures, or whether the application of more sophisticated and complex methods is mandatory.

3. STRONG SHOCKWAVE APPROXIMATION

The propagation of shock waves generated by lightning discharges can be derived from Eulerian conservation equations of mass,

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial r} + \rho \left(\frac{u_r}{r} + \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} \right) = 0 \quad (1)$$

momentum,

$$\frac{\partial u_r}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} = - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} \quad (2)$$

and energy

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho E) + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r \rho u_r \cdot (E + p / \rho)) = 0 \quad (3)$$

in cylindrical coordinates with radial coordinate, density ρ , pressure p , radial velocity u_r and the total internal specific energy, assuming an ideal gas equation of state,

$$E = \frac{1}{\gamma - 1} \frac{p}{\rho} + \frac{1}{2} u_r^2, \quad \gamma = \frac{c_p}{c_v} \quad (4)$$

with the specific heat ratio γ .

According to Lin [23], following coordinate transformation can be performed. Let $R(t)$ be the radius of the shock front and R_0 a characteristic radius to be defined later. That is how we come to the transformations of a non-dimensional radial variable and velocity

$$\eta = r R^{-1}(t), \quad v(\eta, t) = u c_0^{-1} \cdot R(t) R_0^{-1} \quad (5)$$

as well as a non-dimensional density and pressure

$$\Psi(\eta, t) = \ln(\rho \rho_0^{-1}), \quad \Pi(\eta, t) = \ln(p p_0^{-1} \cdot R^2(t) R_0^{-2}) \quad (6)$$

where ρ_0 and p_0 are the values of density and pressure in the undisturbed medium and c_0 the corresponding velocity of sound. If we define the dimensionless time and shock wave radius velocity

$$\tau = c_0 R_0^{-1} t \quad \text{and} \quad \xi = R(t) R_0^{-1} \quad (7)$$

and denote \dot{f} and f' as the derivative with respect to τ and η , we arrive at three differential equations that govern the time dependent spreading of a cylindrical shock wave

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{v} &= (v + v' \cdot \eta) \xi \dot{\xi}^{-1} - \xi^{-2} (v \cdot v' + \gamma^{-1} e^{(\Pi - \Psi)} \cdot \Pi') \\ \dot{\Psi} &= \eta \cdot \Psi' \cdot \xi \dot{\xi}^{-1} - \xi^{-2} (v \cdot \Psi' + v \eta^{-1} + v') \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\dot{\Pi} = (\eta \cdot \Pi' + 2) \cdot \xi \dot{\xi}^{-1} - \xi^{-2} (v \cdot \Pi' + \gamma (v' + v \eta^{-1}))$$

Imposing adiabatic boundary conditions and assuming a constant specific heat γ , our transformations give the following system of boundary conditions at the moving shock front (denoted with "1")

$$\begin{aligned} v_1 &= 2 \xi \dot{\xi} (1 - \xi^{-2}) (\gamma + 1)^{-1} \\ \Psi_1 &= \ln \left((\gamma + 1) (\gamma - 1 + 2 \xi^{-2})^{-1} \right) \\ \Pi_1 &= \ln \left(\xi^2 + 2 \gamma (\gamma + 1)^{-1} \xi^2 \dot{\xi}^2 (1 - \xi^{-2}) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

It is the assumption of a very strong shock wave, $\dot{\xi}^{-1} \rightarrow 0$, and $\xi \ll 1$ first given by Lin [23], i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} v_1 &= 2 \xi \dot{\xi} (\gamma + 1)^{-1} \\ \Psi_1 &= \ln \left((\gamma + 1) (\gamma - 1)^{-1} \right) \\ \Pi_1 &= \ln \left(2 \gamma (\gamma + 1)^{-1} \xi^2 \dot{\xi}^2 \right) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

that leads to a self-similar solution, since the only time dependence is in the term $\xi \dot{\xi}$. The final solution is obtained by assignment $\xi \dot{\xi}$ with the total deposited energy released at $t = 0$ at $r = 0$

$$E_0 = 2 \pi \int_0^R \left(\frac{p}{\gamma - 1} + \frac{\rho}{2} u^2 \right) r dr - 2 \pi \frac{p_0}{\gamma - 1} \int_0^R \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} r dr \quad (11)$$

The right integral can be neglected since the ratio $p_0 \rho / \rho_0$ compared to the left integrand is small. The left integral can numerically be evaluated and further used to arrive at the following expression

$$\xi \dot{\xi} = (c_0 R_0)^{-1} R(t) dR(t) / dt = E_0 (c_0 R_0 \rho_0 \bar{I})^{-1} \quad (12)$$

or

$$R(t) = \left(2 E_0 (\rho_0 \bar{I})^{-1} \cdot t \right)^{1/2} \quad (13)$$

with a numerical constant $\bar{I} = 3.93631$. This value agrees well with the values 3.94 or 3.96 given in literature [11], [22].

Consistent with literature, the characteristic radius is then interpreted as

$$R_0 = \sqrt{4E_0 / (\bar{\Gamma} \gamma p_0)} \quad (14)$$

By a further transformations

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{v} &= v \left(\frac{\xi \dot{\xi}}{\xi} \right)^{-1} \quad \text{with} \quad \bar{v}_1 = 2(\gamma + 1)^{-1} \\ \bar{\Pi} &= \Pi - 2 \ln \left(\frac{\xi \dot{\xi}}{\xi} \right) \quad \text{with} \quad \bar{\Pi}_1 = \ln \left(2\gamma(\gamma + 1)^{-1} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

the velocity, density and pressure can be calculated by integration of the following three differential equations

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{v}' &= \left(\bar{v}(\bar{v} - \eta) + e^{\bar{\Pi} - \Psi} (\bar{v}\eta^{-1} - 2\gamma^{-1}) \right) \left((\bar{v} - \eta)^2 - e^{\bar{\Pi} - \Psi} \right)^{-1} \\ \Psi' &= \left(\bar{v}' + \bar{v}\eta^{-1} \right) (\eta - \bar{v})^{-1} \\ \bar{\Pi}' &= \left(\gamma(\bar{v}' + \bar{v}\eta^{-1}) - 2 \right) (\eta - \bar{v})^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

by means of using any convenient numerical tool.

A few approaches exist to estimate the energy input E_0 of the lightning current components, either based on simple physical reasoning [24], or on correlation of spectral properties of lightning with that of laboratory sparks [19], or on MHD model calculations [14], [26]-[29]. However, still no unique relationship between lightning discharge energy and the emitted shock wave energy is known. As in Ref. [30] we suggest for return strokes a dependency of the peak current as

$$E_0 [\text{J/m}] \approx 0.45 \times 10^{-2} \times (I_{\max} [\text{A}])^{1.25} \quad (17)$$

which gives fairly good consistency with one dimensional, cylinder symmetric MHD-calculations.

It is important to note the limitations of the strong shock wave approximation: First, the strong shockwave approximation is expected to be valid only for small shock front radii $R \ll R_0$. Second, on pressure and overpressure are indistinguishable. Ref. [20] specifies a ratio of $\Delta p/p_0 > 10$ for the validity of the strong shock wave approximation. Third, a constant specific heat ratio is assumed. This does not allow the analysis of real gases, which however might be important, especially in the case of a highly ionized plasma channel.

4. CFD APPROACH

The case at hand is a Riemann problem with a highly compressible gas and non-ideal gas equations are to be considered. Care has to be taken when selecting a numerical solver that can accurately capture the shock front. The software must provide the ability to use or implement appropriate equations of state (EOS). For the present analysis, we employ the blastFoam solver from the open-source toolbox blastFoam Version 5.0 [31], which is based on the OpenFOAM® framework [32]. The numerical method is relying on full finite volume discretization and takes for the present work advantage of the Harten-Lax-van Leer-central wave flux discretization introduced by Toro [33]. The solver blastFoam solves generally the compressible Navier-Stokes equations for a large variety of fluid and explosion models in three dimensions. In the present study, however, we assume an inviscid gas and cylindrical symmetry and ignore all axial effects. Three different equations of states will be compared

- Perfect gas with constant heat capacity $c_p = 1004 \text{ J/kg/K}$, specific gas constant $R = 287 \text{ J/kg/K}$, and $\gamma = 1.4$.

- The EOS of Doan and Nickel [34]. This EOS includes to some extent changes in the composition of air at high temperatures and the variation of the specific heat ratio due to dissociation of molecules.
- The “air₂”-EOS of Plooster [11], [12], which also accounts for molecular changes and is stated by means of two equations, expressing the specific internal energy as function of temperature and pressure as function of temperature and density. However, in order to use the equations in the blastfoam solver, the equations must be numerically solved for temperature and pressure as a function of the specific internal energy and density with high accuracy. The data is transferred to the software as a table. For due resolution, density values between $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg/m}^3$ and $1 \times 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3$ in seven steps and specific energy values between $1.4 \times 10^5 \text{ J/kg}$ and $2.9 \times 10^9 \text{ J/kg}$ in 100 logarithmic steps have proven to be sufficient in the later analysis.

The numerical domain is modelled as a wedge in order to impose cylindrical symmetry. The wedge radius was chosen as 2 m. Due to the imposed symmetry, only one cell layer is required for the axial direction. In the radial direction, a graded mesh with 2500 cells and an expansion ratio of 40 from the innermost to the outermost cell length turned out to be sufficient to achieve mesh independency of the numerical results. Appropriate symmetry and zero gradient boundary conditions for pressure, temperature and velocity are applied at the domain boundaries and the center axis so the pressure wave leaves the domain without reflection.

The initial conditions are taken from the strong shock wave approach: Equations (16) are solved numerically for a given line energy E_0 and initial time or, respectively, shockwave radius using a standard variable step size Runge-Kutta method [35]. The resulting fields are interpolated to the cell centers of the grid. In the remaining domain, we apply atmospheric pressure and the ambient temperature of 300 K.

5. FINITE-ELEMENT CALCULATIONS

Lightning strike loads cause damage to airframe structures by several different physical mechanisms. The thermal damage is caused by the resistive Joule heating, the direct heat conduction and the thermal radiation from the hot plasma channel [8]. The severe mechanical damage of composite structures at and around the lightning attachment area is caused mainly by hemi-spherical shock waves generated by exploding vaporized materials at the arc attachment area. However, the contributions from the shock waves caused by the supersonic expansion of the hot plasma channel and the magnetic volume forces cannot be neglected completely. Meanwhile, physical-based models were developed that accurately describe the lightning-induced mechanical damage of protected carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) structures [4]-[9]. These models were validated on experimental VISAR (Velocity Interferometer System for Any Reflector) results [9]. The finite element method (FEM) calculations were performed using Abaqus/Explicit [10]. A progressive damage analysis, including inter-laminar damage simulation by means of a cohesive zone formulation at the interface between plies, was used to assess the effect of damage on the response of CFRP structures subjected to a lightning strike. A comparison with the predictions of a linear-elastic model was also performed. The numerical results agree

well with experimental VISAR data and provide a valuable insight on the physics of the lightning-induced damage. These numerical simulations showed that appropriate damage models must be considered to correctly describe the dynamic response of the laminated CFRP structures subjected to a lightning strike. Furthermore, the mechanical damage to the composite structure occurs within the first 50 microseconds of the transient lightning load, i.e., within the period the lightning current amplitude drops to 50 % of the maximum value, see the plot of the lightning current load shown in Fig. 1. This means that within this time period, the lightning-induced mechanical forces acting on the fibre composite structure must be described correctly by the numerical models used. Inaccuracies and deviations occurring later may lead to an incorrect description of the elastic vibrations of the structure, but have no influence on the mechanical damage.

6. RESULTS

In the following, we assume a peak current of the lightning component of $I_o = 96.4$ kA [4] or, respectively by means of eq. (17) a line source Energy of $E_o \approx 7.6$ kJ/m (since it is planned to re-evaluate the work of [4] with the present results). In Ref. [4], the experimental lightning current load was fitted to the equation

$$I(t) = \begin{cases} c(e^{-at} - e^{-bt}), & t < t_{\max} \\ c(e^{-ad(t-v)} - e^{-bd(t-v)}), & t \geq t_{\max} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

where t_{\max} is the time at the current peak. For convenience, the parameters for the current waveform with a time to peak of 26.8 μ s, a decay time of 48.5 μ s and a peak current of 96.4 kA are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Waveform parameters for the 26.8/48.5 μ s, 96.4 kA modified double exponential function.

a [s ⁻¹]	b [s ⁻¹]	c [A]	d [-]	v [s]	t_{\max} [s]
3.3833 $\times 10^4$	4.1024 $\times 10^4$	13.617 $\times 10^5$	2.0841	1.392 $\times 10^{-5}$	2.68 $\times 10^{-5}$

Fig. 1. Shock front radius as function of time for different equations of state in comparison to the strong shock wave approximation (SSW). The straight line visualizes a hypothetical expansion with c_o . The current amplitude (right scale) refers to the current wave form of eq. (18).

In Fig. 1 we contrast the expansion of the shock front radius R_{SF} from the computational fluid dynamics (CFD)-calculations with that of the strong shock wave approximation, i.e. eq. (14). The strong shock wave approximation is expected to be valid for $R_{SF} \ll R_o$ with

$R_o \approx 230$ mm, see eq. (14). The results indicate deviations starting at about 40 μ s, when $R_{SF} \approx 60$ mm which is about 0.25 R_o . This occurs beyond the peak time of the current pulse (but slightly less than 50 % decay time of 48.5 μ s). Beyond 40 μ s the propagation velocity of only the CFD calculations transitions smoothly into the acoustic range with a constant propagation velocity. The shock wave front of the ideal gas lags somewhat behind that of the other equations of state. This can be explained by the fact that in the ideal gas with constant γ , dissociation and ionization effects are not considered. This means that less system energy is available compared to the two other equations of state, if identical initial conditions are chosen, as in this work.

Fig. 2. Pressure profiles for short timescales (top) and for the acoustic regime (bottom). Colours correspond to different equations of state or, respectively, the strong shock wave approximation (SSW).

Similar conclusions can be drawn from Fig. 2, which shows the pressure profiles for small time spans and times already from the acoustic range. For times below 40 μ s, the results of the individual calculations agree quite well. For very short times, oscillations within the shock wave radius can still be seen in the CFD calculations, but these decay relatively quickly. Beyond 40 μ s or the overpressure $\Delta p/p_o \approx 0.1$, the quality of the strong shock wave approximation deteriorates rapidly. It should be mentioned that the SSW does not distinguish between gauge pressure and absolute pressure. If one were to assume that it is the absolute pressure, the deviation from the CFD calculation would be much greater in the peak values, but somewhat better in the mean pressure values. Asymptotically, the pressure would drop unphysically to zero in the wake zone. Overall, the bottom picture in Fig. 2 makes it clear that the strong shock wave approximation should not be used in the acoustic range. However, beyond 40 μ s the overpressure $\Delta p/p_o \approx 0.1$ is rather low and does not

contribute to lightning-induced mechanical damage of heterogeneous composite structures.

In case one is only interested in the pressure peaks, Plooster [11] has suggested a correction to increase the range of validity of the SSW approximation. The effect of this correction with the parameters given in [11] for an ideal gas is shown in Figure 3. It is clear that the amplitudes initially go in the right direction, but are overcorrected in the acoustic range.

Fig. 3. Peak pressure as function of time from the simulation and SSW (solid lines) and the SSW with corrections from [11].

Fig. 4. Calculated total force of the propagating shock wave as a function of time.

Figure 4 finally shows the calculated total force of the propagating shockwave (i.e., the overpressure integrated over the surface). For the strong shock wave approximation, it can numerically be shown that the force

$$F(t) = 2\pi \int_0^{R(t)} p(r,t) r dr \cong 0.3179 \times E_o \quad (19)$$

corresponding to the red line in Figure 4. The CFD calculation, on the other hand, shows an initial variation around this value and then goes asymptotically towards a constant value (for larger times). Since both the strong shock wave approximation and the CFD calculation assume an inviscid medium and do not take losses into account, this behavior seems quite plausible, at least for the time periods considered here.

Overall, the strong shock wave approximation gives a reasonable approximation within the time span of the current pulse. From a practical point of view, this is also the significant phase for the lightning-induced mechanical loads acting on the composite structure. Later, the force is distributed over a larger area and will have little effect on the

damage to the structure, but will have a significant effect on elastic deflection behavior (seen in particular in VISAR experiments). However, this has to be examined in detail in a future FEM calculation of the response behavior of the composite structure to an applied lightning current load.

A mathematically simple but physical-based method for correcting the pressure profile in the acoustic range is to use the following scaling function:

$$s(\eta) = C \frac{e^{\bar{\eta}(\eta)} - \max(e^{\bar{\eta}(\eta)})}{\max(e^{\bar{\eta}(\eta)}) - \min(e^{\bar{\eta}(\eta)})} + K \quad (20)$$

$$p_{corrected}(\eta) = p(\eta) \cdot s(\eta)$$

where K is Plooster's [11] correction factor for the peak pressure. For every time instant, the parameter C is chosen so that the total force remains constant. In addition, the shock-front-radius is modified by replacing the red line in Fig. 1 with the dashed straight line from the point where the velocity of the shock front drops to the speed of sound of the ambient region. Typical results are shown in Fig. 5. With reference to Fig. 2 and in comparison to the CFD-results, this scaling method significantly improves the agreement in the acoustic range. The propagation speed cannot drop under the speed of sound. Furthermore, even a negative gauge pressure within the shock front radius can be reproduced with this correction.

Fig. 5. Corrected pressure profiles in the transition to the acoustic range (top) and corresponding correction functions (bottom).

7. CONCLUSIONS

The rapid temperature rise of the lightning plasma channel generates an outward propagating shock wave during the initial phase of the lightning current rise time. The temporal and spatial propagation of the shockwaves and pressures needed for simulation of lightning-induced mechanical damage of composite structures are derived from semi-analytical and numerical CFD computations. The CFD

simulations show that the magnitude of the shock front radius depends in principle on the equation of state used, but only outside the range of the validity of the strong shockwave approximation. The peak pressure of the shock wave given by the strong shock wave approximation is generally lower than that given by the CFD simulations with different equations of state. The peak value can be easily adjusted using Plooster's correction formula. However, the pressure profile within the shock wave radius must then be corrected so that the force acting on the composite structure is not affected by this correction.

The magnitude of the overpressure $\Delta p/p_0$ beyond the radii and time range of the strong shock wave approximation is rather low. The mechanical damage of protected composite structures occurs mainly in the early stage transient lightning current component. Moreover, the mechanical damage is caused mainly by the explosion of vaporized lightning protection measure, since this contribution is considerably larger than this of the outward propagating shock wave. Therefore, the rather small overpressure beyond the radii and time range of the strong shock wave approximation does not contribute to lightning-induced mechanical damage of heterogeneous composite structures.

Overall, it is shown that the strong shock wave approximation, which provides reliable results for the very early stage of shock wave formation, is adequate to correctly describe the mechanical damage of composite structures. However, beyond the range of validity of the strong shock wave approximation corrections in the transition range between the shock wave propagation and acoustic wave propagation are needed, in particular the too low propagation velocity of the shock wave. The proposed scaling procedure not only accounts for the Plooster's correction for the amplitude of the shock wave front but also provides a correct, physically based behaviour of the pressure profile within the shock wave front. This is especially important if one wants to interpret experimental VISAR results (as in [36] – [38]) or correlate them with FEM calculations: Due to the inertia of the system, the deflections are also strongly influenced by the shock wave in the acoustic range. On the other hand, the structural damage is more likely to occur due to the very short-time phenomena in the SSW range. A simple back-calculation of experimentally measured vibration amplitudes to the total experienced impulse is also critical to handle because of the dissipation that occurs.

Finally, care should be taken when simply adding the pressures from the surface explosion and the lightning shock wave, as the underlying physics is non-linear. More detailed investigations should be informative here.

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